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WORKER'S LIFTING TECHNIQUES IN HARDWARE STORE: AN ERGONOMIC STUDY

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DEDICATION

The Almighty God, who has been their source of guidance during this entire research process, is the one to whom the researchers would want to sincerely dedicate their work. His heavenly presence and steadfast assistance have given them the courage, insight, and motivation they need to overcome obstacles and succeed.

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ABSTRACT

Title : WORKER'S LIFTING TECHNIQUES IN
HARDWARE STORE: AN ERGONOMIC STUDY

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The study entitled, "Worker's Lifting Techniques in Hardware Store: An Ergonomic Study" is a detailed investigation into various lifting activities carried out by personnel in hardware stores about the various ergonomic hazards. It will also explain how lifting techniques can affect musculoskeletal health and promote ergonomic recommendations that enhance workplace safety. This study is designed in a way that it can provide the quantification of ergonomic risk factors, which may potentially identify injury risk factors through direct observation and assessment by tools like Rapid Entire Body Assessment, the National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health Lifting Equation, and Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaire. The research stresses ethical considerations, protecting participants' privacy and safety while ensuring their involvement is valued throughout the study process. The study's findings have the potential to help shape new legislation or policies targeted at enhancing workplace safety and health, which will benefit both workers and the wider public.

Keywords: Lifting techniques, ergonomics, CMDQ, REBA, NIOSH, risk factors.

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CHAPTER 1

THE PROBLEM AND ITS SCOPE

INTRODUCTION

Rationale of the Study

The hardware industry frequently exposes workers to substantial physical stress, repetitive tasks, and substandard ergonomic conditions. Consequently, this contributes to a heightened prevalence of work-related injuries and illnesses, resulting in reduced productivity, escalated medical expenses, and diminished worker morale (Susihonoa & Adiatmikab, 2021). To address these challenges comprehensively, the industry must prioritize ergonomic solutions and enforce robust safety protocols. This may involve the provision of adjustable workstations, ergonomic tools, and regular training on proper lifting techniques. Moreover, encouraging regular breaks and task rotations can reduce the risk of repetitive strain injuries. By investing in employee well-being, the industry fosters a safer work environment and cultivates heightened productivity, reduced turnover, and enhanced employee satisfaction.

The physical demands placed on workers within these establishments can lead to various occupational hazards, particularly related to musculoskeletal injuries. Implementing ergonomic practices is paramount in mitigating these risks and ensuring the well-being of workers (Mock et al., 2017). According to the United States Bureau of Labor Statistics, overexertion and bodily reaction are the leading

causes of non-fatal injuries in the retail industry, with a significant portion occurring in hardware stores (Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2021).

The perceptions and attitudes toward safety and ergonomics within hardware stores play a pivotal role in determining the efficacy of safety measures. Often, there may be a prevailing attitude that associates heavy lifting with the nature of the job, leading to a normalization of the risks related to such tasks. This can create a barrier to the implementation of ergonomic practices. It was discovered that most hardware store employees recognized the dangers linked to lifting heavy objects, there was a prevalent belief that injuries were an inherent part of the job and could not be entirely prevented (Bonaccio et al., 2020).

Implementing improved ergonomic practices should be a top priority for hardware stores globally, as evidenced by high injury rates linked to physical job demands across multiple countries. Statistics reveal hardware retail workers face ergonomic risks 2-3 times greater than other industries (CCOHS, 2022), with manual handling accounting for 60-70% of reported injuries internationally (Davies et al., 2002). The predominant injuries of back strains, sprains, and musculoskeletal disorders result in substantial lost time, diminished quality of life, and increased workers' compensation costs (National Retail Federation, 2021; Colombini et al., 2016).

The clear occupational hazard of excessive physical exertion and its severe consequences warrant urgent action. Ergonomic controls such as lifting equipment, task rotation, training in safe techniques, and improved store layouts

reduce injury rates and severity (Occupational Safety and Health Administration [OSHA], 2018).

The implementation of ergonomic practices in hardware stores can significantly reduce the risk of injury and improve overall worker safety by reducing exposure to physical stress, minimizing repetitive tasks, and providing a safe and comfortable work environment (Jonathan & Mbogo, 2016). According to ILO estimates, 250 million work accidents occur each year, with an additional 160 million suffering from work-related illnesses. Furthermore, around 1.2 million people die as a result of such accidents and illnesses, resulting in a 4% economic loss in total global GNP.

One of the key challenges in implementing ergonomic practices in hardware stores is the lack of understanding and awareness among workers and managers. Many workers may not be aware of the potential benefits of ergonomic practices, and managers may not understand the importance of investing in ergonomic equipment and training. In the United States, there are over 19,000 hardware stores that provide machinery, power tools and equipment, timber, paint and sundries, plumbing fixtures and supplies, hand tools and accessories, and much more. Retail establishments, from high-end boutiques to hardware stores, provide several hazards that might result in employee injuries (Risk Mitigation Strategy for Hardware Stores | AmTrust Financial, n.d.).

The incidence rate of occupational injury in the Philippines is 4.27 percent, implying that there are around 4 occurrences of occupational injury with workdays lost per 100 workers (View of Trend of Work-related Injuries in the Philippines from

2010-2020, n.d.). The National Capital Region (NCR) or Metro Manila region has the greatest proportion of work-related injury cases (16.3%), followed by CALABARZON (12.8%) and Central Visayas (11.3%). All workers in various vocations deserve the best possible physical, mental, and social well-being, as well as protection against hazardous workplace situations that can lead to ill health impacts, accidents, and fatalities (View of Trend of Work-related Injuries in the Philippines from 2010-2020, n.d.).

To enhance the awareness and understanding of ergonomic practices in hardware stores, education and training programs can be implemented. These programs can provide workers with information about the potential benefits of ergonomic practices, as well as safe and effective ways to use ergonomic equipment (National Center for Biotechnology Information, 2024).

Despite the challenges, the implementation of ergonomic practices can provide significant benefits for hardware store workers. These benefits include reduced physical stress, decreased exposure to repetitive tasks, and a comfortable and safe work environment (OSH 2023). The reduction in physical stress can lead to improved health and well-being, while the decreased exposure to repetitive tasks can help to prevent injuries and illnesses. A comfortable and safe work environment can also improve worker morale, leading to increased productivity and job satisfaction.

The researchers will analyze and improve ergonomic practices and worker safety in the hardware retail industry, with a focus on Musculoskeletal Disorders or Discomfort (MSD) caused by heavy lifting. To explore this, the researchers will look

at the pain or discomfort that hardware store porters have when lifting big goods, as well as offer recommendations to improve worker safety against musculoskeletal disorders in hardware stores. This study will help further develop the body of knowledge in multiple fields, inform future research efforts, and potentially lead to the creation of new tools and interventions that encourage ergonomic practices and increase worker safety.

In conclusion, researchers sought to show that the implementation of ergonomic practices in hardware stores can significantly reduce the risk of injury and improve overall worker safety. By providing education and training programs, investing in high-quality ergonomic equipment, and fostering a culture of ergonomics, hardware store managers can reduce the physical stress of their workers, minimize the risk of repetitive tasks, and create a safe and comfortable work environment. The implementation of these practices can provide significant benefits for workers, managers, and the entire hardware industry, leading to improved efficiency, customer satisfaction, and productivity.

Theoretical Background

In any job, ensuring workers' safety and well-being is critical. This study digs into the critical topic of worker safety in hardware stores.

This study is anchored on the Gate Control Theory of Pain, published by Ronald Melzack and Patrick Wall in *Science* in 1965, this well-known concept proposes that sensory, emotional, and cognitive elements all interact to influence pain perception. It emphasizes the importance of individual variability in pain perception and coping techniques. This theory proposes that nerve stimuli can be prevented from reaching the thalamus and cerebral cortex by inhibiting them at the level of the substantia gelatinosa and the dorsal horn of the spinal cord (Melzack & Wall 1983). The gate control theory is used to advocate for the use of massage and strokes like effleurage during labor. These modalities are thought to distract the brain from the pain messages it is processing (Turk, 2001).

Figure 1. Gate Control Theory of Pain (Melzack & Wall 1983).

According to this theory shown in Figure 1, a system in the spinal cord allows pain signals to be transferred up to the brain to be processed to amplify or attenuate pain at the spinal cord level. This was classified into two categories such as the open gate and close gate. The explanation states as follows:

Open Gates. When the gates are open, you experience much too much anguish for far too long. People suffering from chronic pain have gates that remain open even when they should be closed (Wendt, 2022b).

Closed Gates. If you've ever had two parts of your body damaged at the same time, you know that pain signals "compete" for our brain's attention. It is tough for your brain to process pain from both regions simultaneously. Self-relaxation techniques and medication are two other methods for closing some gates (Wendt, 2022b).

Also, according to the related theory, the neuromatrix theory of pain, developed by Ronald Melzack represents an expansion beyond his original "gate theory" of pain, first proposed in 1965 with P. D. Wall. Some fundamental parts of the gate theory of pain are retained in the neuromatrix pain theory, but it provides a more thorough framework for understanding the subjectivity of pain. It acknowledges the importance of both ascending and descending inputs to the conscious sensation of pain and incorporates other inputs not included in the gate theory, such as memory and prior experiences (Trout, 2004).

This study investigates worker safety in hardware stores, with a focus on the Gate Control Theory of Pain, which proposes that sensory, emotional, and

cognitive factors interact to determine pain perception. The idea stresses individual differences in pain perception and coping strategies. It implies that nerve stimuli can be blocked at the substantia gelatinosa and dorsal horn of the spinal cord, preventing them from reaching the thalamus and cerebral cortex. The paper also describes how the spinal cord opening and closing gates can increase or reduce pain. Ronald Melzack's neuromatrix theory of pain, which incorporates both ascending and descending inputs as well as memory, provides a more thorough account of pain subjectivity.

This study integrates the Cornell Musculoskeletal Disorder Questionnaire, NIOSH Lifting Equation, and REBA to assess ergonomic risks among hardware store workers. The Cornell Questionnaire provides a baseline for identifying musculoskeletal symptoms linked to poor ergonomics (Çakıt, E. 2019). The NIOSH Lifting Equation evaluates manual lifting risks, ensuring appropriate weight limits (Waters et al., 1993). REBA assesses postural risks, highlighting concerns with awkward movements and repetitive tasks (Hignett & McAtamney, 2000). In conclusion, these assessments provide a comprehensive view of workplace risks, guiding ergonomic improvements to reduce musculoskeletal disorders and enhance worker safety.

Figure 2. Theoretical Framework.

This study's theoretical framework integrates the Gate Control Theory of Pain (Melzack & Wall, 1965) and the Neuromatrix Theory of Pain (Melzack, 2001) to explore worker safety in hardware stores. According to the Gate Control Theory, sensory, emotional, and cognitive elements impact how you feel pain, indicating that the central nervous system can manipulate pain signals at the spinal cord level. In contrast, the Neuromatrix Theory expands this understanding by incorporating memory, prior experiences, and bidirectional pain inputs, highlighting that pain involves a complex interplay of biological, psychological, and social factors (Woolf & Mannion, 2015). To assess these factors, the study employs three key ergonomic assessment methods: Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaire (CMDQ) (Sternlicht et al., 2018): Developed at Cornell University, this self-reported questionnaire measures musculoskeletal discomfort in various body regions. It links ergonomic factors such as awkward postures, repetitive motions, and heavy lifting to discomfort levels, providing valuable data for targeted interventions. Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) (Hignett & McAtamney, 2000): This systematic tool evaluates ergonomic risks associated with different tasks by examining workers' posture and movements. It scores various body regions to identify potential musculoskeletal issues and prioritize risk reduction interventions. Revised NIOSH Lifting Equation (RNLE) (Waters et al., 1993): This tool, developed by the National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health, calculates the risk for back injuries from manual lifting tasks. It takes into account factors such as the weight of the load, the distance it is lifted, and the frequency of lifting, helping to prevent musculoskeletal disorders related to lifting and lowering tasks. Ultimately, the framework informs potential ergonomic interventions and safety improvements, including proper

lifting techniques and workplace optimizations, to enhance worker safety in hardware stores (**Kumar & Bhattacharya, 2019**).

Review of Related Literature

Hardware stores are dynamic workplaces that bring a variety of physical hazards to employees. While traditional safety regulations are important, developing a culture of workers regarding safety through ergonomic interventions can prevent injuries and enhance well-being. This review of the literature looks at the existing research on the junction of perception of workers' safety, ergonomics, and their application in hardware stores. It investigates the unique issues that hardware store porters confront, assesses the effectiveness of ergonomic treatments in improving safety, and identifies gaps in the present knowledge base. The sequel of this related literature was as follows:

1. ERGONOMIC ASSESSMENT TOOLS

1.1 Manual Material Handling

Rajendran et al. (2021) analyze various variables that trigger the prevalence of MSDs especially among workers in the research they did, "Ergonomic evaluation of workers during manual material handling," They highlight issues such as insufficient job knowledge, inexperience, carelessness, and poor working postures as significant risk factors. The researchers outline their data collection methods and analyze lifting tasks across various industries using the NIOSH lifting equation for risk assessment. Their findings reveal that the lifting index often exceeds acceptable limits, indicating a substantial risk of MSDs. In order to improve worker safety, the authors stress the

significance of addressing ergonomic issues with manual handling, particularly while lifting, lowering, pushing, and pulling. They advise using appropriate lifting techniques and following particular ergonomic standards. In addition, they recommend the creation of educational initiatives aimed at increasing knowledge of safe lifting techniques, which may help to considerably lower the rate of MSDs at work.

1.2 NIOSH Lifting Equation

According to the study by Arjmand et al. (2015), manual material handling (MMH) and lifting activities are significantly linked to an increased incidence of low back pain (LBP). The National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) lifting equation estimates the Recommended Weight Limit (RWL) by adjusting a constant weight of 23 kg using six multipliers—horizontal (HM), vertical (VM), asymmetry (AM), distance (DM), coupling (CM), and frequency (FM)—each ranging from 0 to 1. These multipliers are calculated based on the load's horizontal and vertical positions relative to the feet, its asymmetry to the body's midsagittal plane, the vertical lift distance, hand-to-load coupling, and lifting frequency. The estimation considers physiological limits on energy expenditure (2.2 to 4.7 kcal/min), psychophysical limits ensuring weight acceptability for 75% of female workers, and biomechanical limits on compressive force at the L5-S1 vertebra (maximum 3400 N). These findings highlight the multifaceted nature of LBP risks associated with MMH and the need for a thorough evaluation of lifting tasks to protect worker health.

1.3 Posture Analysis

The substantial prevalence of musculoskeletal conditions associated with impoverished posture while at work highlights a critical issue in work environments that depend extensively on manual tasks (Rizkya et al., 2024), "Evaluation of Work Posture and Quantification of Fatigue by Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA)." By employing the REBA method, they found that many workers were often in positions that put them at significant risk for injuries, with 62% of the tasks assessed needing immediate attention to improve safety. This study reveals not only the physical toll of these awkward postures but also how they contribute to worker fatigue. The results provide as an essential warning of how important it is to give ergonomic techniques top priority at work. By making necessary adjustments and encouraging better techniques, companies can help protect their workers from discomfort and injuries while boosting overall productivity and well-being.

1.4 Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaire

The Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaire (CMDQ) has been thoughtfully adapted for Turkish speakers, significantly improving its ability to assess musculoskeletal discomfort in this population. This process involved careful translation, synthesis, back-translation, expert review, and pretesting, resulting in the Turkish version known as the T-CMDQ. In a study with 48 employees from a metal manufacturing company, researchers evaluated the T-CMDQ's validity and reliability. They found strong agreement between the responses on the visual analog scale and the frequency scale, along with positive

correlations between visual analog scale scores and severity scale scores of the T-CMDQ across different body areas. The T-CMDQ also showed good test-retest reliability and internal consistency, affirming its effectiveness as a reliable tool for understanding musculoskeletal discomfort (Erdoğan et al., 2011).

2. WORK SAFETY MEASURES

2.1 Training and Education Programs

In an effort to enhance safety and prevent musculoskeletal injuries in factories, we created a real-time lifting technique monitoring system that emphasizes the importance of training and education programs. Using a Microsoft Kinect camera, the system tracks workers' movements at 30 frames per second, analyzing their joint angles to identify unsafe lifting postures. By first observing how each worker lifts, it personalizes feedback based on their unique strengths and limitations, recommending the safest and most efficient techniques. This tailored approach not only empowers workers to lift with confidence but also fosters a culture of learning and awareness around proper lifting practices. The study shows that by addressing common unsafe habits, we can promote long-term behavior changes, ultimately creating a healthier and safer work environment for everyone involved. It's like having a supportive coach by your side, guiding you every step of the way to ensure you stay safe while doing your best work (Lunin & Glock, 2021).

2.2 Communication and Reporting System

Establishing communication and reporting mechanisms is crucial, for enhancing safety, within the hardware store sector. Encouraging employees to express their safety worries and pinpoint potential dangers promotes a safety culture. Holding frequent safety gatherings distributing safety updates and implementing suggestion boxes can cultivate an atmosphere of transparency enabling team members to exchange their perspectives and observations. Providing reporting avenues also grants employees the confidence to voice their concerns without hesitation. Establishing communication channels is crucial, in addressing any safety concerns within an organization to proactively implement preventive measures and enhance safety protocols consistently. Prioritizing communication and teamwork allows businesses to cultivate a safety environment that safeguards employees while also boosting operational efficiency and customer service standards (SafetyStratus Research Advisory Groups report, from 2023).

Figure 3. Review of Related Literature Structure.

To improve worker safety, the hardware store's ergonomic practices can be evaluated using the conceptual framework shown in Figure 3. It describes the many elements that go into a thorough ergonomic assessment, such as the Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaire, posture analysis, ergonomic assessment instruments, communication and reporting systems, work safety precautions, and training and educational initiatives. Together, these elements can be used in a thorough ergonomic evaluation to find possible risks, evaluate them, and put the right interventions in place to increase worker safety in the hardware shop.

THE PROBLEM

Statement of the Problem

Musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) are a major global health concern, impacting millions of people and resulting in severe pain, disability, and economic costs. The hardware retail industry is distinguished by a dynamic and physically demanding work environment wherein employees are exposed to the risk of musculoskeletal injuries. Assessing current practices can assist in establishing a safer and more productive workplace. This study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the workers, in terms of:
 - a. Age;
 - b. Work Experience; and,
 - c. BMI (Height & Weight)
2. What NIOSH score poses the highest risk level of musculoskeletal disorder on a specific lifting task?
3. What characteristics of lifting a bag of cement at the hardware store contribute to the highest risk of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs)?
4. What are the respondents' perceptions of pain and discomfort according to the Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaire?

5. What ergonomic intervention can be crafted from the hardware store to reduce the risk of musculoskeletal disorders (MSD)?

Significance of the Study

The study entitled “Worker’s Lifting Technique in Hardware Store: An Ergonomic Study” will be of great benefit to the following:

Hardware Store Workers. This study will help the hardware store workers improve their musculoskeletal health, reduce pain and discomfort, and also serve as a source of educational understanding. Additionally, this will serve as an evidence-based recommendation for improving ergonomic practices, implementing ergonomic training and development programs among workers about work conditions or procedures, addressing the utilization of proper lifting techniques that provide efficiency and convenience in practice, and assessing risk management.

Hardware Store Owners and Managers. This study will help them identify the potential cause of workplace injuries and accidents, and this may be able to assess situations, including ergonomic training and development programs, and enhance the overall operation. Furthermore, this will mitigate the potential issues such as the cost associated with the improper lifting of loads of the workers causing them to be susceptible to risk, productivity, employee morale, public relations or reputation, regulatory compliance, and market differentiation or competitive advantage.

Policymakers. The study's findings can be used to inform the establishment of new legislation or policies requiring companies to implement ergonomic practices, presumably leading to a broader impact on workplace safety across diverse industries.

The General Public. The study aids to a safer and healthier society for everyone by improving the safety and health of workers at hardware stores.

Future Researchers. This research study will be one of the related instruments used by future researchers undertaking comparable studies. It will serve as a reference and a guide to help them improve their academics.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section discussed the methodologies utilized for this study and the researchers' process to answer the problems formulated.

Method

This study evaluates the ergonomic risks related to lifting procedures employed by employees in a hardware shop using a quantitative observational research method. Through direct worker observation, while they lift cement sacks, the study aims to quantify ergonomic risk factors. Participants who regularly do manual material handling jobs are chosen for the study using a purposive sampling technique. The sample size will be decided by worker availability, with a target range of 30–50 participants to assure statistical validity.

The NIOSH Lifting Equation, the Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA), and the Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaire (CMDQ) are the three ergonomic evaluation instruments used to collect data. The suggested weight limitations and the physical strain involved in lifting the cement bags will be determined using the NIOSH Lifting Equation. Workers will be given risk scores based on their posture, movement, and lifting mechanics after their body posture is evaluated using REBA. Workers' self-reported data regarding their subjective musculoskeletal pain and discomfort during lifting duties will be collected by the CMDQ.

Additionally, this study takes into consideration work-related variables such as the age of respondents (years), Body Mass Index BMI: weight/height kg/cm

and workers' experience that may influence lifting behavior among the individuals besides their risk for handling injuries. The challenge is to identify areas most in need of ergonomic change and make improvements that can help reduce injuries among hardware store workers.

Research Flow of the Study

This study evaluates the ergonomic risks related to workers' lifting procedures using a methodical manner. Purposive or convenience sampling is used to identify the target group, which includes employees at hardware stores. The physical load is evaluated and suggested weight limits are computed using the NIOSH Lifting Equation, REBA, and CMDQ. The CMDQ (Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaire) is used to collect self-reported data on musculoskeletal discomfort, pain intensity, and frequency of discomfort felt by workers after completing the activity.

The gathered data is arranged and entered into software or a spreadsheet for additional analysis. The data is summarized using descriptive statistics, and correlation analysis is done to investigate the connections between self-reported discomfort and physical characteristics. Important ergonomic hazards that have been linked to an increased risk of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) include awkward postures, high loads, and inadequate lifting procedures. Suggestions are made to enhance lifting methods and lower dangers; these include workstation arrangement adjustments, load weight optimization, and training on safe lifting techniques.

A thorough report that includes evidence-based suggestions for enhancing worker safety and lowering the risk of MSDs summarizes and presents the findings. Stakeholders, including the management of hardware stores, are informed of the findings to consider workable solutions to improve worker health and safety.

Figure 4. Research Flow of the study.

Figure 4 presents the research path for a hardware store ergonomics study. Defining the objectives for the study and researching for a review of related literature are the first steps in the process. The next steps include determining the responsibilities of hardware store employees, surveying and observing them, and writing a transmittal letter. Data collection, analysis, and interpretation occur after approval. Data collection and analysis are done using assessment instruments such as the NIOSH Lifting Equation Calculator, Ergonomics Ruler for Angle Measurement, and Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaire. Based on the findings, a set of ergonomic improvements and proposals are being made. The study concludes with a presentation of conclusions and recommendations.

Research Environment

The research was conducted in the Municipality of Badian, and Ronda, Cebu Province. There are four hardware stores such as MEB hardware at Banhigan, Badian; DUDZ Enterprise at Poblacion, Badian; Floremi Enterprise at Poblacion, Ronda; and, DUDZ Enterprise at Poblacion, Ronda. The hardware stores provide a wide range of products and services, most of which focus on home improvement and upkeep. This allows the researchers for an in-depth analysis of various tasks involving lifting and helps identify specific ergonomic risk factors that may not be present in other work settings.

Figure 5. Map of South Cebu Province along with target research environment.

The figure above shows a map of South Cebu Province, highlighting specific target research environments. The highlighted locations on the map include four establishments: Dudz Enterprise – Badian, Floremi Enterprise, Dudz Enterprise – Ronda, and MEB Hardware.

Participants

There are four (4) hardware stores from different municipalities as areas of the research study. The population was between the age of 29 – 42. The ergonomic risk analysis uses a method, the National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) Lifting Equation, constituted with the Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaire (CMDQ), and the Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA). The mean values and the standard differences between age, work experience, and body mass index (BMI) of the individuals were 35 ± 5.67 years, 42 ± 18 months, and 21.76 ± 0.85 , respectively (Table 1). The participants were briefed about the study, and by signing a participatory agreement form, then expressed their willingness to participate. Before completing the questionnaire and work evaluation, the participants were provided with and instructed to read the information letter.

Variables	MEB	DUDZ B	FLOREMI	DUDZ R	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum
Age (yr)	38	32	42	29	35.4303	5.67479	29	42
Work Experience (month)	45	20.36	64.5	41.6	42.8659	180.179	20.36	64.5
Height (cm)	165.2	166.53	163.07	167.41	165.554	1.89026	163.07	167.41
Weight (kg)	59.7	62.73	54.5	61.73	59.6652	3.6667	54.5	62.73
Body Mass Index (kg/cm)	21.88	22.44	20.53	22.19	21.7614	0.85238	20.53	22.44

Table 1: Demographic Statistics

This section provides an overview of the physical and demographic traits of the study participants, with an emphasis on factors like age, weight, height, work experience, and Body Mass Index (BMI) that can have an impact on musculoskeletal discomfort. The study's participants range in age from 29 to 42 years old and in length of employment from 20.36 to 64.5 months. Their weights vary from 54.50 kg to 62.73 kg, and their heights range from 163.07 cm to 167.41

cm, which is rather similar. According to the BMI results, which vary from 20.53 to 22.44, every worker is classified as being within the normal weight range.

A worker's physical work capacity decreases with age, with a notable average decline of 20% between ages 40 and 60. This is due to reductions in aerobic and musculoskeletal capacity (indicating a substantial decrease in ability over time). As we age, our sensory abilities (e.g. hearing and vision) and physical fitness (e.g. aerobic capacity, muscular strength, endurance, flexibility, body composition, and balance) gradually deteriorate (Kenny et al., 2016). Older working adults are more likely to experience physical decline after the age of 50, leading to a higher prevalence of age-related disorders, reduced mobility and quality of life, and increased use of health care and medication (Poscia et al., 2016). Employers are increasingly using workplace physical activity treatments, recognizing their potential to improve health and work performance (Tringali, n.d.).

Research Instrument

The NIOSH Lifting Equation, REBA, and CMDQ are the research tools used in this study. Among these, the NIOSH Lifting Equation is the principal tool for determining the physical burden associated with lifting operations. It considers characteristics such as load weight, lifting distance, frequency, and posture to provide a quantitative estimate of the task's physical demands. REBA, on the other hand, assesses entire body posture while lifting and assigns scores depending on the postures of various body components. Finally, the CMDQ assesses the incidence of musculoskeletal disorders among workers by gathering data on symptoms, pain intensity, and the impact of these disorders on everyday activities.

Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaire (CMDQ)

The Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaires (CMDQ) were created by Cornell University ergonomics graduate students and Dr. Alan Hedge (Hedge et al., 1999). There are multiple-choice, forced, and structured versions of this questionnaire. It identifies the sections of the body that are more likely to experience musculoskeletal issues and has 60 elements for 20 different body parts. The twenty bodily parts—the neck, shoulders, upper back, upper arms, lower back, forearms, wrists, hip/buttocks, thighs, knees, lower legs, and foot—are shown on a body-map diagram. All participants received the questionnaire, and to get their answers, the individuals were interviewed one-on-one. To score the subjects' discomfort in the following areas, the questionnaire is divided into three sections: (1) frequency of ache, pain, or discomfort; (2) intensity of ache, pain, or discomfort; and (3) interference of ache, pain, or discomfort with work (Yusof & Shalahim, 2021). According to CMDQ scoring guidelines, a worker's specific body part's overall discomfort score can be calculated by multiplying the discomfort scores for frequency, intensity, and interference in the following way:

Figure 6. Flow Diagram showing the CMDQ scoring from the questionnaire details.

Figure 6 shows the Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaire (CMDQ) employs a three-factor scoring system: interference, discomfort, and frequency. To measure the degree of musculoskeletal discomfort felt, each

element is given a numerical value. The frequency, unpleasantness, and interference scores are multiplied to obtain the overall discomfort score. This methodology offers a thorough assessment of musculoskeletal pain, supporting the examination of the effects of particular activities or environments.

Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA)

In this study, the Ergonautas Ruler Software was utilized as a critical tool for assessing ergonomic risks at the lifting loads station. This software allowed for precise measurement of body segment angles, focusing on postures that might contribute to musculoskeletal disorders. Using the REBA (Rapid Entire Body Assessment) method within the Ergonautas platform, images of the worker were analyzed to accurately evaluate postural risks. The REBA method, developed by Hignett and McAtamney, involves assigning scores to postures based on body part diagrams. The scores obtained are then used to assess the likelihood of musculoskeletal problems (Hignett and McAtamney, 2000).

The RULER tool specifically enabled the researchers to measure the angular displacement between different body segments, ensuring correct angle capture of the worker's posture during task execution. These angular measurements were critical for applying the REBA method, which divides the body into two segments: Group A (trunk, neck, and legs) and Group B (upper arms, lower arms, and wrists). Postures for each group were scored using pre-determined flexion and extension degrees, with additional load/force scores integrated into the assessment.

To determine how serious the ergonomic problem was, the final risk score—which varied from negligible risk (1) to very high risk (11+)—was calculated using the aggregate REBA ratings for the two groups. This final score is pivotal in identifying ergonomic risks and determining necessary interventions, such as corrective action or further assessment, to enhance worker safety and comfort during lifting tasks. The REBA scoring indicator and action levels are shown in Table 2.

REBA Score	Risk Level	Action Level
1	Negligible	No action required
2-3	Low	Modification may be needed
4-7	Medium	Further investigation may be needed
8-10	High	Modification is required
>11	Very High	Modification is required immediately

Table 2. The risk score in the REBA method and associated action levels.

NIOSH Lifting Equation

According to Okimoto and Teixeira (2008), six task variables are given weights by a multiplicative model, which forms the basis of the NLE. The weights are represented as coefficients that are used to lower the load constant, which is the highest load weight that is suggested to be lifted under ideal circumstances.

The RWL is obtained through the following equation:

$$\mathbf{RWL = LC \times HM \times VM \times DM \times AM \times FM \times CM}$$

To assess manual lifting tasks, RNLE suggested a recommended weight limit (RWL). The multipliers that make up the 1991 NIOSH lifting equation are dependent on the input variables.

Figure 7. Representation of the task variables. Source: NIOSH (1994). (A) Graphic representation of variables H and V . (B) Graphic representation angle of asymmetry.

The NIOSH Lifting Equation task variables are shown in Figure 7 and include the angle of asymmetry, lengths in both vertical and horizontal directions, and the projection of the connection midpoint onto the frontal plane. The risk of musculoskeletal injury during lifting tasks is estimated using these factors.

After determining the RWL for a certain manual lifting activity, the object's actual weight is compared to the computed number. The Lifting Index (LI), which is a measure of the physical stress associated with the task being evaluated, is provided by this relationship (Okimoto & Teixeira, 2008). This estimate of physical stress levels is defined by the following equation:

$$LI = L/RWL$$

where L is the Load weight or weight of the object lifted (in kg) and RWL is the Recommended Weight Limit (in kg).

The RWL and LI are predicated on the idea that as lifting tasks become more demanding, so does the risk of lower back pain (LBP) associated with the job. Put differently, the risk of LBP rises with the size of the LI (Waters et al., 1993; NIOSH, 1994). It is well known that a task is safe if the LI is 1.0 or lower. Some workers may find their employment to be risky if the LI is greater than 1.0. A job with a LI of 3.0 is not twice as dangerous as a job with a LI of 1.5; rather, the higher the LI, the less safe the employment is (Garg, 1995).

Data Gathering Procedure

The study's data collection process will be carried out in phases. Participants will initially be chosen from among hardware shop employees who regularly lift cement bags. Before continuing, each subject will be asked for their informed consent. First, demographic information will be gathered, including age, height, weight, and employment experience, among other pertinent characteristics. After that, participants will be shown lifting a typical 40-kg cement bag on camera, guaranteeing a variety of perspectives for precise analysis. Using an ergonomic checklist, researchers will monitor and document participants' posture, motions, and lifting techniques throughout each lifting job.

The NLE Calculator will be used in this study to evaluate systematically lifting data, allowing for the measurement of essential characteristics such as load weight, lifting frequency, horizontal and vertical distances, and lift start and finish heights. Using the NLE Calculator, researchers want to identify potential dangers and prescribe safe lifting procedures to reduce musculoskeletal discomfort among workers at hardware stores. To spot any departures from safe procedures, instruments such as the Ergonautas Ruler will be utilized to monitor important body angles during lifting. Following the task, participants will self-report any pain or discomfort they encountered during or after lifting by completing the Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaire (CMDQ). After that, the information will be gathered and analyzed to evaluate lifting methods, pinpoint injury risk factors, and guide ergonomic advancements.

Ethical Consideration

The research titled "Worker's Lifting Techniques in Hardware Store: An Ergonomic Study" will prioritize ethics by safeguarding the privacy and safety of participants and ensuring their participation is respected throughout the study process. Before gathering any data, the research project is to commence in earnest after obtaining consent from participants by providing them with explanations of the study's objectives and methods as well, as any potential risks involved. Participants will be assured that their involvement is entirely optional and they are free to withdraw at any point without experiencing any consequences.

Protect the privacy of participants by anonymizing data and securely storing video recordings and other identifiable information for access, by authorized researchers only. The data will remain confidential and solely utilized for research purposes. All lifting tasks will be conducted in a setting, with safety protocols implemented to minimize hazards and prevent any injuries throughout the research. If participants encounter any discomfort or physical strain during the study they are allowed to stop their involvement.

Finally, the study will make sure that no dishonest methods are employed, and participants will receive a debriefing that includes an explanation of the results and suggestions for enhancing their lifting methods and lowering their risk of injury.

STATISTICAL TREATMENT

In this section, the researchers acquired the data, which has been analyzed in Chapter 2. The statistical approach done for each method is as follows:

REBA Score. The study's goals are to evaluate the required or chosen body position, intense exertions, movement or action type, repetition, and coupling (Matt, 2014). Hence, the researchers utilized descriptive statistics that provide a fundamental understanding of the distribution of REBA scores within a population of hardware store workers.

Interpretation: The final REBA score is interpreted as follows:

Score	Level of MSD Risk
1	Negligible risk, no action required
2-3	Low risk, change may be needed
4-7	Medium risk, further investigation, change soon
8-10	High risk, investigate and implement change
11+	Very high risk, implement change

NIOSH Score (Lifting Index). The Lifting Index (LI) is then calculated by dividing the actual weight of the object being lifted by the RWL. An LI of:

Less than **1.0** indicates a low risk of injury for most healthy workers.

Between **1.0** and **3.0** indicates an increased risk of injury for some workers, depending on individual factors.

Greater than **3.0** indicates a high risk of injury for most workers.

Hence, descriptive statistics has been utilized to summarize the data and compute the means, standard deviations, and ranges of the important variables (such as weight lifted, advised weight limits, and lifting index).

CMDQ. The study utilized the analysis of variance (ANOVA) in one direction to ascertain if the means of several groups or treatments differ statistically significantly, hence offering insights into the variability of data under various circumstances.

CHAPTER 2

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter thoroughly examines the research study's findings, emphasizing statistical aspects, work responsibilities, and the frequency of musculoskeletal discomfort. Trends, associations, and insights are highlighted for easy comprehension.

NIOSH LIFTING EQUATION

The NLE Calculator (NIOSH Calculator) software program generated the analyses and suggestions for each task listed below. This program assesses the risk of back strain from prolonged hard lifting. When determining the Recommended Weight Limit and Lifting Index using the Revised NIOSH Lifting Equation, weight, height, distance, frequency, posture, and other pertinent data collected are taken into account (Warner et al., 2017). The software makes suggestions for safer lifting workouts that reduce the risk of injury. With NLE Calc, businesses can protect employee health and safety, increase productivity, and improve worker safety.

MEB HARDWARE STORE

The lifting task described in this data has a maximum weight of 110 pounds and an average load of 88 pounds. The weight is raised vertically from 33 to 70 inches with a vertical travel distance of 373 inches, perhaps throughout several lifts. The horizontal distance between the body and the load is between 22 and 24

inches. There is significant torso twisting as indicated by the asymmetry angle, which begins at 43° and increases slightly at 46°. Three lifts per minute are performed at a moderate frequency during the task length. The grip quality is graded as "fair," indicating that managing the weight can be challenging. Ergonomic dangers arise from large weights, twisting, and repeated lifting.

ACTUAL MEASUREMENTS	ORIGIN	DESTINATION
Load Weight (L) (pounds)	Ave: 88	Max: 110
Load Constant (pounds)	51	51
Horizontal Location (H) (inches)	24	22
Vertical Location (V) (inches)	33	70
Vertical Travel Distance (Vo-Vd)	373	
Asymmetry Angle (A) (degrees)	43	46
Lifting Duration (hours)	MODERATE	
Lifting Frequency (F) (lifts/minute)	3	
Coupling (C)	FAIR	

Table 3. NIOSH Lifting Equation Manual Scoring in NLE Calc Software.

Figure 8. Angle of Asymmetry: Lifting a bag of cement weighing approximately

88 lbs.

The angle of asymmetry during the hoisting of a cement bag weighing around 88 pounds is shown in Figure 8. The amount of torso twisting during the lift

is indicated by the asymmetry angle. At the beginning of the lift, there is moderate twisting indicated by the angle of 43 degrees. The worker's body appears to twist even further when the bag is transferred, as indicated by the asymmetry angle rising to 46 degrees as the task continues.

Lifting a 40 kg (88 lbs) cement bag onto a truck for MEB demonstrates considerable effort, with a high lifting index of 9.4 indicating a severe risk of injury. This task's evaluation under the SLI framework would incorporate its high-demand nature and potential repetitive strain related to other tasks performed. Understanding the physical impact of this lift within the work cycle will inform safety measures, as the SLI calculation can guide adjustments to working practices to mitigate injury risk (University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, 2024).

CALCULATION DETAILS			RECOMMENDATION
ACTUAL MEASUREMENTS	ORIGIN	DESTINATION	
Lifting Constant (LC)	51.00	51.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bring the load closer to the worker by removing any horizontal barriers or reducing the size of the object. Lifts near the floor should be avoided; if unavoidable, the object should fit easily between the legs. - Raise/lower the origin/destination of the lift. Avoid lifting near the floor or above the shoulders. Reduce the lifting frequency rate, reduce the lifting duration, or provide longer recovery periods (i.e. light work period). -Move the origin and destination of the lift closer together to reduce the angle of twist, or move the origin and destination further apart to force the worker to turn the feet and step, rather than twist the body. Reduce the vertical distance between the origin and the destination of the lift. - Eliminate the need for significant control of the object at the destination by redesigning the job or modifying the container/object characteristics.
Horizontal Multiplier (HM)	0.42	0.45	
Vertical Multiplier (VM)	0.98	0.70	
Distance Multiplier (DM)	0.87	0.87	
Asymmetry Multiplier (AM)	0.86	0.85	
Frequency Multiplier (FM)	0.79	0.79	
Coupling Multiplier (CM)	1.00	1.00	
Recommended Weight Limit (RWL)	12.40	9.40	
Frequency Independent RWL (FIRWL)	15.70	11.90	
Single Task RWL (STRWL)	12.40	9.40	
Frequency Independent (FI)	7.00	9.20	
Single Task LI (FILI)	7.10	9.40	
Lifting Index (LI)	7.10	9.40	

Table 4. Calculation Results using NLE Calc.

DUDZ ENTERPRISE POBLACION, BADIAN, CEBU

This data shows a lifting operation with a maximum load weight of 110 pounds and an average load weight of 88 pounds. 51 pounds is the load constant, which provides a safe lifting standard. A vertical travel distance of 472 inches is achieved, perhaps over several repeats, with a horizontal reach of 19 to 20 inches and a vertical lift of 46 to 59 inches. The asymmetry angle exhibits a reduction in torso twisting, starting at 51° and decreasing to 47°. The lifting length is brief—one lift per minute—and the grip quality is assessed as "fair." However, even with this little duration, there are ergonomic concerns associated with high weights and significant twisting.

ACTUAL MEASUREMENTS	ORIGIN	DESTINATION
Load Weight (L) (pounds)	Ave: 88	Max: 110
Load Constant (pounds)	51	51
Horizontal Location (H) (inches)	19	20
Vertical Location (V) (inches)	46	59
Vertical Travel Distance (Vo-Vd)	472	
Asymmetry Angle (A) (degrees)	51	47
Lifting Duration (hours)	SHORT	
Lifting Frequency (F) (lifts/minute)	1	
Coupling (C)	FAIR	

Table 5. NIOSH Lifting Equation Manual Scoring in NLE Calc Software.

Figure 9. Angle of Asymmetry: Lifting a bag of cement weighing approximately 88 lbs.

The angle of asymmetry during the hoisting of a cement bag weighing around 88 pounds is shown in Figure 9. The asymmetry angle shows how far the body twisted during the lift. The angle is measured at 51 degrees at the beginning, indicating a strong twisting at the beginning of the lifting operation. The angle gets smaller as the lift goes on, coming down to 47 degrees, indicating that the worker's torso gets closer to the load as it is raised.

This task is quantified by a Lifting Index (LI) of 5.8, indicating a high level of risk when lifting a bag of cement onto a truck. The Lifting Index is determined using the NIOSH Lifting Equation, which accounts for critical factors including the weight of the cement bag and the height and distance of the lift. The calculated value suggests that the task exceeds safe lifting limits for most workers, posing a considerable risk for injuries. Factors such as frequency of lifts and grip strength further emphasize the strenuous nature of this task. Consequently, ergonomic improvements—such as reducing lifting frequency or adjusting the load's

proximity—are vital for reducing the associated risks and improving worker safety during this strenuous task. Cole et al. (2004) calculated forces using LIs ranging from 4.5 to 5.5 kN to investigate lumbar spine loads during lifting activities. The study sheds light on the risk of low back problems at work and safe load handling.

CALCULATION DETAILS			RECOMMENDATION
ACTUAL MEASUREMENTS	ORIGIN	DESTINATION	
Lifting Constant (LC)	51.00	51.00	Bring the load closer to the worker by removing any horizontal barriers or reducing the size of the object. Lifts near the floor should be avoided; if unavoidable, the object should fit easily between the legs.
Horizontal Multiplier (HM)	0.53	0.50	
Vertical Multiplier (VM)	0.88	0.78	
Distance Multiplier (DM)	0.96	0.96	- Raise/lower the origin/destination of the lift. Avoid lifting near the floor or above the shoulders.
Asymmetry Multiplier (AM)	0.84	0.85	- Move the origin and destination of the lift closer together to reduce the angle of twist, or move the origin and destination further apart to force the worker to turn the feet and step, rather than twist the body.
Frequency Multiplier (FM)	0.94	0.94	
Coupling Multiplier (CM)	1.00	1.00	
Recommended Weight Limit (RWL)	18.00	15.30	Reduce the lifting frequency rate, reduce the lifting duration, or provide longer recovery periods (i.e. light work period).
Frequency Independent RWL (FIRWL)	19.20	16.20	
Single Task RWL (STRWL)	18.00	15.20	
Frequency Independent (FI)	5.70	6.80	Reduce the vertical distance between the origin and the destination of the lift.
Single Task LI (FILI)	4.90	5.80	
Lifting Index (LI)	4.90	5.80	Eliminate the need for significant control of the object at the destination by redesigning the job or modifying the container/object characteristics.

Table 6. Calculation Results using NLE Calc.

DUDZ ENTERPRISE RONDA, CEBU

This data depicts a lifting task with a load constant of 51 pounds and an average load weight of 88 pounds with a maximum load weight of 110 pounds. The load and body are separated horizontally by a distance of 16 to 18 inches. A vertical travel distance of 175 inches is achieved when the vertical lift shifts from 47 to 50 inches. As the lift increases, the asymmetry angle lowers to 31° from 81°, which indicates severe twisting. This indicates improved alignment. With a frequency of one lift per minute, the lifting duration is brief, and the grip quality is graded as

"fair." The high starting twisting angle draws attention to potential ergonomic concerns related to this lifting task.

ACTUAL MEASUREMENTS	ORIGIN	DESTINATION
Load Weight (L) (pounds)	Ave: 88	Max: 110
Load Constant (pounds)	51	51
Horizontal Location (H) (inches)	16	18
Vertical Location (V) (inches)	47	50
Vertical Travel Distance (Vo-Vd)	175	
Asymmetry Angle (A) (degrees)	81	31
Lifting Duration (hours)	SHORT	
Lifting Frequency (F) (lifts/minute)	1	
Coupling (C)	FAIR	

Table 7. NIOSH Lifting Equation Manual Scoring in NLE Calc Software.

Figure 10. Angle of Asymmetry: Lifting a bag of cement weighing approximately 88 lbs.

The angle of asymmetry during the hoisting of an approximately 88-pound cement bag is shown in Figure 10. The amount of torso twisting during the lifting motion is measured by the asymmetry angle. The angle is measured at 81 degrees at the beginning of the lift, which indicates a considerable degree of twisting that

may present a risk for musculoskeletal strain. The angle drops to 31 degrees as the lifting gets more intense, indicating that the worker's body moves more in line with the load and lessens the strain on the torso and back.

This task also involves considerable physical effort, with an LI of 4.5. It takes into account multiple lifting factors, indicating that it too exceeds safe lifting thresholds for workers, thus posing a high risk of injury. The focus here would be on strategies to bring the load closer during the lift, diminish the frequency of lifts, and employ better grip techniques to alleviate the musculoskeletal stress associated with this type of lifting action. For the SLI process, the input from this task's time fractions and maximum lifting index would be essential in calculating the overall stress of the sequential lifting job. Smeets et al. (2011) investigated ergonomic techniques for minimizing back pain in industrial environments with high LI. Lifting loads with high LI values is connected with back injuries, indicating the need for task change.

CALCULATION DETAILS			RECOMMENDATION
ACTUAL MEASUREMENTS	ORIGIN	DESTINATION	
Lifting Constant (LC)	51.00	51.00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bring the load closer to the worker by removing any horizontal barriers or reducing the size of the object. Lifts near the floor should be avoided; if unavoidable, the object should fit easily between the legs. - Move the origin and destination of the lift closer together to reduce the angle of twist, or move the origin and destination further apart to force the worker to turn the feet and step, rather than twist the body. - Raise/lower the origin/destination of the lift. Avoid lifting near the floor or above the shoulders. - Reduce the lifting frequency rate, reduce the lifting duration, or provide longer recovery periods (i.e. light work period).
Horizontal Multiplier (HM)	0.63	0.56	
Vertical Multiplier (VM)	0.87	0.85	
Distance Multiplier (DM)	1.00	1.00	
Asymmetry Multiplier (AM)	0.74	0.90	
Frequency Multiplier (FM)	0.94	0.94	
Coupling Multiplier (CM)	1.00	1.00	
Recommended Weight Limit (RWL)	19.40	20.50	
Frequency Independent RWL (FIRWL)	20.70	21.80	
Single Task RWL (STRWL)	19.50	20.50	
Frequency Independent (FI)	5.30	5.00	
Single Task LI (FIL)	4.50	4.30	
Lifting Index (LI)	4.50	4.30	

Table 8. Calculation Results using NLE Calc.

FLOREMI RONDA, CEBU

This data describes a lifting task with a load constant of 51 pounds and an average load weight of 88 pounds with a maximum load weight of 110 pounds. The vertical lift occurs between 27 and 18 inches, resulting in a vertical travel distance of 402 inches, whereas the horizontal distance from the body to the load ranges between 15 and 25 inches. The asymmetry angle, which rises to 42 degrees from 34 degrees at the beginning of the lift, suggests some torso twisting. The combination of mild twisting and large loads suggests potential ergonomic concerns. The lifting time is brief, with one lift per minute, and the grip quality is assessed as "fair."

ACTUAL MEASUREMENTS	ORIGIN	DESTINATION
Load Weight (L) (pounds)	Ave: 88	Max: 110
Load Constant (pounds)	51	51
Horizontal Location (H) (inches)	25	15
Vertical Location (V) (inches)	27	18
Vertical Travel Distance (Vo-Vd)	402	
Asymmetry Angle (A) (degrees)	34	42
Lifting Duration (hours)	SHORT	
Lifting Frequency (F) (lifts/minute)	1	
Coupling (C)	FAIR	

Table 9. NIOSH Lifting Equation Manual Scoring in NLE Calc Software.

Figure 41. Angle of Asymmetry: Lifting a bag of cement weighing approximately 88 lbs.

The angle of asymmetry during the hoisting of a cement bag weighing around 88 pounds is shown in Figure 8. The asymmetry angle quantifies the extent to which the body twists during the lift. At 34 degrees in the beginning, there will be some twisting as the lift progresses. The task's asymmetry angle rises to 42 degrees as it goes along, indicating increased twisting as the load is transferred.

Lifting a bag of cement onto a Floremi truck presents substantial physical challenges, with a calculated Lifting Index (LI) of 5.5. This index reflects a moderate to high level of risk, suggesting that the lifting task exceeds safe limits due to multiple contributing factors, such as the lift height, distance from the body, and the frequency of lifts. As with the previous task, an LI above 1.0 signifies potential injuries can arise from these strenuous conditions. To effectively manage the associated risks, the implementation of improved lifting techniques or the use of mechanical aids is highly recommended. This approach is crucial for minimizing physical strain on workers engaged in such demanding tasks. Pentikis (2017) researched lifting safety by examining tasks with LIs of 4.5 or higher. The findings

underline that exceeding these LIs may raise injury risk, making the study relevant for tasks with lifting limits.

CALCULATION DETAILS			RECOMMENDATION
ACTUAL MEASUREMENTS	ORIGIN	DESTINATION	
Lifting Constant (LC)	51.00	51.00	<p>Bring the load closer to the worker by removing any horizontal barriers or reducing the size of the object. Lifts near the floor should be avoided; if unavoidable, the object should fit easily between the legs.</p> <p>- Move the origin and destination of the lift closer together to reduce the angle of twist, or move the origin and destination further apart to force the worker to turn the feet and step, rather than twist the body.</p> <p>- Raise/lower the origin/destination of the lift. Avoid lifting near the floor or above the shoulders.</p> <p>- Reduce the lifting frequency rate, reduce the lifting duration, or provide longer recovery periods (i.e. light work period),</p> <p>- Improve the hand-to-object coupling by providing optimal containers with handles or handhold cutouts, or improve the handholds for irregular objects.</p>
Horizontal Multiplier (HM)	0.40	0.67	
Vertical Multiplier (VM)	0.98	0.91	
Distance Multiplier (DM)	1.00	1.00	
Asymmetry Multiplier (AM)	0.89	0.87	
Frequency Multiplier (FM)	0.94	0.94	
Coupling Multiplier (CM)	0.95	0.95	
Recommended Weight Limit (RWL)	15.90	24.20	
Frequency Independent RWL (FIRWL)	16.90	25.70	
Single Task RWL (STRWL)	15.90	24.20	
Frequency Independent (FI)	6.50	4.30	
Single Task LI (FILI)	5.50	3.60	
Lifting Index (LI)	5.50	3.60	

Table 10. Calculation Results using NLE Calc.

CORNELL MUSCULOSKELETAL DISCOMFORT QUESTIONNAIRE (CMDQ)

Body Region	Frequency Score	Discomfort Score	Interference Score	Total Discomfort Score	Total Discomfort Score (Percentage)
Neck	50	22	21	23100	12.45%
Shoulder (right)	68	29	30	59160	31.88%
(left)	68.5	27	27	49936.5	26.91%
Upper Back	61.5	28	33	56826	30.62%
Upper Arm (right)	72	24	24	41472	22.35%
(left)	67	21	23	32361	17.44%
Lower Back	84	47	47	185556	100.00%
Forearm (right)	55.5	18	23	22977	12.38%
(left)	50.5	15	21	15907.5	8.57%
Wrist (right)	18.5	13	16	3848	2.07%
(left)	20	15	17	5100	2.75%
Hip/Buttocks	70.5	25	27	47587.5	25.65%
Thigh (right)	51	20	19	19380	10.44%
(left)	49.5	21	19	19750.5	10.64%
Knee (right)	57.5	22	27	34155	18.41%
(left)	55.5	21	27	31468.5	16.96%
Lower Leg (right)	58	24	22	30624	16.50%
(left)	53.5	21	19	21346.5	11.50%
Foot (right)	24.5	13	11	3503.5	1.89%
(left)	23	11	10	2530	1.36%

Table 11. Total Discomfort Score Perceived of the Hardware Store Workers.

The information in the table above is a study on musculoskeletal or ergonomic discomfort, which evaluated the degree and effects of physical pain in different body areas for a group of participants.

According to findings, there are certain portions experiencing greater discomfort than of the others in different body parts. The lower back is the most affected body part, scoring 100% of the potential Total Discomfort Score. Aziz et al. (2017) conducted a study on assembly line workers and discovered that lower back pain from manual lifting duties scored high on the CMDQ. This study

underlines how repetitive motion and lifting jobs might lead to chronic back problems. This suggests that the lower back is frequently quite painful at work, which can be problematic for jobs that require prolonged standing, sitting, or heavy lifting.

With percentages of 31.88% and 30.62%, respectively, the Right Shoulder and Upper Back also exhibit notable discomfort, suggesting that these areas are also severely affected. Mean et al. (2013) investigated ergonomic concerns in the metal stamping sector, with an emphasis on discomfort in the right shoulder and upper back caused by heavy lifting. This study confirmed the CMDQ as a tool for assessing repeated strain and suggested changed lifting practices. Poor posture, overhead activity, and repetitive upper body movements are all known to put strain on these areas, which could be the cause of this.

In a similar vein, the Hip/Buttocks region's 25.65% discomfort percentage indicates that extended sitting or poor seating ergonomics may be factors in this area's discomfort. Estember and Que (2020) investigated ergonomic discomfort in warehouse workers in the courier sector, finding considerable hip and buttock discomfort ratings associated with repetitive lifting. The study suggested participative ergonomic measures to reduce discomfort.

Nevertheless, the wrist (right) with the score of 2.07% and the foot (left) with a score of 1.36% of its degree of discomfort poses the lowest. Even though the study showed no discomfort in these body areas, they may nevertheless require attention in specific work environments, particularly those that include repetitive hand movements or extended standing. Sortillón-González et al. (2024)

investigated musculoskeletal discomfort among sculptors, focusing on specific issues in the right wrist and left foot. Although discomfort was lower in these places, repetitive stress posed a risk, implying tailored actions to reduce strain even in less affected areas. The right upper arm, right lower leg, and right knee are other places that are a little uncomfortable.

Anova: Single
Factor

SUMMARY

<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
Frequency Score	20	1058.5	52.925	339.0861842
Discomfort Score	20	437	21.85	60.87105263
Interference Score	20	463	23.15	65.50263158

ANOVA

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	12359.30833	2	6179.654167	39.82934676	1.50235E-11	3.158842719
Within Groups	8843.7375	57	155.1532895			
Total	21203.04583	59				

Table 12. ANOVA Single Factor Statistical Analysis of the Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaire (CMDQ).

In this study, a one-way ANOVA was conducted to examine differences in the Frequency Score, Discomfort Score, and Interference Score among workers. According to the descriptive statistics, there was a significant difference between the average frequency of discomfort (52.93) and the average discomfort score

(21.85) as well as the average interference score (23.15). This implies that although discomfort is experienced by employees regularly, the degree of it and its effect on their work is relatively moderate. With an F-value of 39.83 and a p-value of $1.50E-11$, which is much less than the conventional significance criterion of 0.05, the ANOVA findings demonstrated a statistically significant difference between these three scores. The null hypothesis is rejected as a result of this compelling evidence, which shows that the means of the frequency, discomfort, and interference scores are not equal.

These results suggest that a complete strategy that targets lowering discomfort frequency as well as minimizing its intensity and disruption of work performance is necessary to effectively treat workers' discomfort. The findings highlight how multiple aspects of pain impact workers and how each influences how they perceive danger overall.

RAPID ENTIRE BODY ASSESSMENT (REBA)

The figures below show the different postural angles of each parameter, while the tables show the analysis of each score. Group A and B scoring procedures consist of four parameters, whereas, Group A analyzes the neck, trunk, and leg for postural angle and adds its posture score to the load score that determines the weight of load thus, also causing the worker to shock or rapid build-up of force, on the other hand, Group B analyzes the upper arm, lower arm, and wrist for postural angle and adds its posture score to the coupling score. Upon administering the scores of Groups A and B, this determines the score of Table C, where the REBA score will exhibit by adding the activity score which refers to the duration and frequency of the task being assessed, specifically focusing on how dynamic or repetitive the worker's posture and movement are.

MEB Hardware Badian, Cebu

Figure 12. Postural Angle of Neck, Trunk, and Legs for REBA.

Figure 13. Postural Angle of Upper Arm, Lower Arm, and Wrist for REBA.

Parameter	Score	Description
Neck	+2	The flexion angle of the neck is 4°.
Trunk	+1	The flexion angle of the trunk is 1°.
Legs	+2	The flexion angle of the leg is 18° and 1 leg is raised.
Force/Load Score	+2	The load weighs 40kg or 88 lbs.
Upper Arm	+5	The flexion angle of the upper arm is at 118° while the shoulder is raised during lifting.
Lower Arm	+2	The flexion angle of the lower arm is 135°.
Wrist	+2	The flexion angle of the wrist is 15°.
Coupling Score	+0	Well fits the handle and mid-range power grip.

Table 13. REBA Employee Assessment Worksheet Analysis of scores.

In this task, the worker is lifting a bag of cement with a one-man carry two-man lift approach, implying collaboration with another individual. The worker

exhibits a posture where the back is relatively straight, and the knees are flexed, aiding in weight distribution. The neck is slightly inclined forward, which might suggest a need for awareness of the lifting load. The upper and lower arms are utilized effectively, maintaining a close grip, as indicated by a moderate coupling score. The REBA score of 9 here shows a high-risk level, indicating that to lower the risk of musculoskeletal problems, the work needs more research and modifications. A sign of risk involved in the task at hand. The worker chose a posture that required bending the knees and leaning forward; this put a strain on their back as well as arms and legs. To minimize the risk of injuries opting for interventions, like mechanical aids or adopting better lifting techniques is advised (as suggested by Zhao et al., 2022).

Figure 18. REBA Score of Lifting a bag of cement weighs 40kg or 88 lbs.

DUDZ Enterprise Badian, Cebu

Figure 15. Postural Angle of Neck, Trunk, and Legs for REBA.

Figure 16. Postural Angle of Upper Arm, Lower Arm, and Wrist for REBA.

Parameter	Score	Description
Neck	+2	The flexion angle of the neck is in extension and at 26°.
Trunk	+2	The flexion angle of the trunk is in extension and at 14°.
Legs	+3	The flexion angle of the leg is 51° and 1 leg is raised.
Force/Load Score	+2	The load weighs 40kg or 88 lbs.
Upper Arm	+4	The flexion angle of the upper arm is at 39° while it's abducted and the shoulder is raised.
Lower Arm	+2	The flexion angle of the lower arm is 170°.
Wrist	+3	The flexion angle of the wrist is 24° and is bent from the midline.
Coupling Score	+1	Acceptable but not ideal hand hold or coupling acceptable with another part.

Table 14. REBA Employee Assessment Worksheet Analysis of scores.

The worker lifts another bag of cement, this time under the one-man carry one-man lift approach. The posture displays a combination of knee bending and slight forward leaning at the waist, which raises concerns regarding back strain. The neck is tilted forward, and the arms are stretched to support the added weight, potentially putting extra stress on the upper body. The activity score is notably consistent, maintaining a level of activity requiring attention. The REBA score of 11 signifies a very high-risk level, inquiring about ergonomic changes to lower the risk of harm. The position required leaning and bending the knees exerting pressure, on the body and legs. Making modifications could reduce these hazards according to Rajendran et al. research in 2021.

Figure 17. REBA Score of Lifting a bag of cement weighs 40kg or 88 lbs.

DUDZ Enterprise Ronda, Cebu

Figure 22. Postural Angle of Neck, Trunk, and Legs for REBA.

Figure 23. Postural Angle of Upper Arm, Lower Arm, and Wrist for REBA.

Parameter	Score	Description
Neck	+2	The flexion angle of the neck is 23°.
Trunk	+2	The flexion angle of the trunk is 15°.
Legs	+2	The flexion angle of the leg is 20° and 1 leg is raised.
Force/Load Score	+2	The load weighs 40kg or 88 lbs.
Upper Arm	+6	The flexion angle of the upper arm is at 167° while it's abducted and the shoulder is raised.
Lower Arm	+2	The flexion angle of the lower arm is 174°.
Wrist	+3	The flexion angle of the wrist is 30° and is bent from the midline.
Coupling Score	+1	Acceptable but not ideal hand hold or coupling acceptable with another part.

Table 15. REBA Employee Assessment Worksheet Analysis of scores.

This task involves a one-man carry two-man lift of a bag of cement again, characterized by a somewhat strained posture. The upper body is inclined forward, and the knees are flexed, which indicates an attempt to lift correctly but suggests potential for back strain. The arms are mostly straight, which may increase the load

on the shoulders. The coupling score is high, denoting good grip strength. With a REBA score of 11, the assessment indicates a very high-risk level, pointing out that even though the worker maintains a grip, the posture could be adjusted to reduce strain. Based on the assessment, lifting a 40 kg cement bag in this task yielded a REBA score of 11—indicating a high-risk level—due, to neck and trunk flexions and suboptimal wrist posture as pointed out by Dedhiya and colleagues in their recent study (2022).

Figure 24. REBA Score of Lifting a bag of cement weighs 40kg or 88 lbs.

FLOREMI Hardware Ronda, Cebu

Figure 21. Postural Angle of Neck, Trunk, and Legs for REBA

Figure 22. Postural Angle of Upper Arm, Lower Arm, and Wrist for REBA.

Parameter	Score	Description
Neck	+1	The flexion angle of the neck is 19°.
Trunk	+2	The flexion angle of the trunk is 10°.
Legs	+2	The flexion angle of the leg is 23° and 1 leg is bent.
Force/Load Score	+3	The load weighs 40kg or 88 lbs and there's a shock or rapid build-up of force.
Upper Arm	+5	The flexion angle of the upper arm is at 170° and the shoulder is raised.
Lower Arm	+2	The flexion angle of the lower arm is 171°.
Wrist	+3	The flexion angle of the wrist is 29° and is bent from the midline.
Coupling Score	+1	Acceptable but not ideal hand hold or coupling acceptable with another part.

Table 16. REBA Employee Assessment Worksheet Analysis of scores.

A worker uses good ergonomics by lifting a cement bag while bending his or her knees slightly and hunching over. Trunk upright, arms close to the torso, and neck neutral. But there could be strain from the upper arm posture. A strong grasp is indicated by the high coupling score. A high-risk level necessitating ergonomic changes is indicated by a REBA score of 11. The employee exhibited bending in the neck and trunk along, with bending in the legs. It is important to implement measures to reduce the likelihood of injuries (Source; Soleman & Priaydi 2021).

Figure 30. REBA Score of Lifting a bag of sand weighs 40kg or 88 lbs.

CHAPTER 3

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter presents a concise overview of the research findings, summarizing the results, and trends observed for recommendation. This chapter also presents the analysis of the different methods and their response to the problems reflected in Chapter 1.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The NIOSH Lifting Equation was utilized in the study to evaluate the lifting risks related to various operations carried out by employees in hardware stores. According to Choi et al. (2012), understanding the weights of popular construction materials can help construction workers decrease their risk exposure. Neglecting this could cause workers to experience pain or injuries.

Figure 24. Lifting Index (LI) carried out at the different hardware stores.

The results of the study are as given in Figure 24. It shows the Lifting Index (LI) carried out to various hardware stores.

Figure 25. Discomfort in body regions.

On figure 25, depicts discomfort levels in various bodily locations as a percentage of overall discomfort. It indicates that lower back is the most uncomfortable, with the lower back about 100%. Widia et al. (2024) conducted an ergonomic risk assessment among warehouse workers and discovered that manual lifting caused considerable lower back pain. The CMDQ results indicated that heavy lifting and uncomfortable postures were main contributors. The study suggested that mechanical aids and workflow redesigns could ameliorate the high rates of back discomfort. The data point to a potential emphasis on the lower back, upper back, and right shoulder for more examination or intervention to alleviate discomfort.

The REBA score of "9" for the "Hardware" category indicates a high-risk level, implying that workers in this configuration are at a significant risk of acquiring ergonomic-related injuries if changes are not implemented. According to Bumrungham, T. (2023), a study concentrating on a logistics service provider showed a REBA score of 9 for particular lifting procedures, prompting actions such as enhanced handling equipment and optimized lifting techniques to reduce ergonomic risks associated with repetitive strain. Higher scores in the other configurations (11 for "MEB," "DUDZ Badian," "DUDZ Ronda," and "Floremi") suggest an even larger risk, underlining the need for immediate intervention. REBA rating values typically range from 1 (very low risk) to 15 (very high risk), with scores of 9 or more indicating high to extremely high ergonomic danger. Kavus, Tas, and Taskin (2023) assessed ergonomic risks for service workers using a hybrid neural network and REBA method. A score of 11 indicated high-risk postures, particularly in conventional manual tasks where ergonomic tools were limited. The study focused on how hybrid techniques can improve REBA's risk identification. This is depicted in table. Alias and Shamsudin (2023) used REBA to estimate the risk of low back pain among healthcare professionals in community clinics, concluding that lifting and handling heavy things contribute significantly to ergonomic strain.

Hardware	MEB	DUDZ Badian	DUDZ Ronda	Floremi
REBA Score	9	11	11	11

Table 17. REBA Scores in different hardware store.

The NIOSH, REBA, and CMDQ methodologies for determining musculoskeletal risk and discomfort are contrasted in this table. Each technique has a unique scoring methodology. For example, NIOSH employs the Lifting Index (LI), and an injury risk is considered to be high if the LI is greater than 1.0. A score of more than four indicates a high risk of MSDs. REBA assigns values between 0 and 15. A score of 0 to 100 is provided by the CMDQ, with scores more than 50 denoting substantial levels of musculoskeletal discomfort. NIOSH assumes a set lifting capacity and does not account for individual variability. REBA involves a decision on which side of the body to examine. CMDQ is subjective and may not correctly reflect the actual amount of danger or discomfort. All three methods have limitations. These approaches provide contrasting viewpoints for evaluating ergonomic hazards and worker discomfort levels.

Method	NIOSH	REBA	CMDQ
Purpose	To evaluate the risk of injury from manual lifting tasks	To evaluate the risk of musculoskeletal disorders from manual handling tasks	To assess the level of musculoskeletal discomfort experienced by workers
Type of Assessment	Quantitative	Quantitative	Qualitative
Assessment Criteria	Weight, distance, height, frequency, posture, and coupling	Posture, load, and movement	Body region, frequency, and severity of discomfort
Scoring System	Lifting Index (LI)	REBA score (0-15)	Discomfort score (0-100)
Interpretation	LI > 1.0 indicates a high risk of injury	REBA score > 4 indicates a high risk of musculoskeletal disorders	Discomfort score > 50 indicates a high level of musculoskeletal discomfort
Limitations	Does not account for individual variability, assumes a fixed lifting capacity	Necessity to decide which side to observe	Subjective assessment, may not accurately reflect the level of risk or discomfort

Table 18. General Characteristics of the NIOSH, REBA, and CMDQ.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it is evident that manual lifting and handling procedures pose major ergonomic dangers in a variety of employment situations, particularly hardware stores and warehouses. The use of several evaluation approaches, such as the NIOSH Lifting Equation, REBA, and CMDQ, has provided useful insights into musculoskeletal discomfort and ergonomic hazards faced by workers. The high scores and percentages associated with pain levels in specific physical areas, such as the lower back, upper back, and right shoulder, highlight the critical need for action to reduce worker discomfort and the risk of ergonomic-related injuries.

The NIOSH score of 9.4 indicates a high risk of musculoskeletal disorders on lifting a bag of cement. The Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaire reveals that respondents' judgments of pain and discomfort are centered on the lower back, upper back, and right shoulder, indicating a significant level of discomfort in these physical areas. This underscores the critical need for ergonomic interventions to relieve discomfort and reduce the risk of ergonomic-related injuries among workers undertaking heavy-lifting duties in hardware stores.

The REBA score of "9" and "11" for the "Hardware" category indicates a high-risk level, meaning that workers in this arrangement are at a great risk of developing ergonomic-related injuries if improvements are not made. This emphasizes the need of ergonomic treatments in lowering the risk of musculoskeletal disorders (MSD) in the hardware shop.

As a result, it is critical to develop targeted ergonomic interventions in hardware stores to lower the risk of musculoskeletal disorders (MSD). These treatments could include improved handling equipment, optimal lifting techniques, and workflow redesigns to reduce ergonomic dangers associated with repetitive strain while also improving workers' general well-being. Such interventions are significant for promoting a safer and healthier work environment while also addressing the unique problems associated with heavy-lifting duties in hardware stores.

RECOMMENDATION

The research entitled "Worker's Lifting Technique in Hardware Store: An Ergonomic Study" is highly significant for increasing workplace safety and efficiency, particularly in physically demanding jobs like manual lifting in hardware stores. When workers handle big things like cement sacks, poor technique and inappropriate ergonomic measures can result in musculoskeletal injuries, decreased efficiency, and long-term health problems. Based on the study's findings, here are some significant recommendations for improving lifting practices and reducing injury risks:

1. Training on Proper Lifting Techniques

Proper lifting techniques can greatly reduce stress on the spine and other joints, which is essential for securely handling big goods such as cement sacks. "Training in lifting" by S. Lavender et al. (2002), published in *Professional Safety*, focuses on a systematic strategy to training workers in lifting practices, thereby lowering the dangers associated with improper lifting. This study stresses that teaching workers proper lifting techniques considerably minimizes the likelihood of musculoskeletal injuries. Workers who participated in structured training programs had improved body mechanics, less spinal strain, and a greater understanding of safe lifting techniques, particularly in repetitive activities. The study indicated that training is critical for long-term ergonomic gains in workplaces requiring heavy manual lifting.

2. Ergonomic Assessment and Workspace Design Improvements

Conduct an extensive ergonomic examination of the workplace. Adjust the shelf heights and storage configurations to reduce bending and reaching. Place heavy things, such as cement sacks, on lower shelves near the ground to keep workers from lifting from an awkward height. The ergonomics body posture on repetitive and heavy lifting activities of workers in aerospace manufacturing warehouse" by S.R. Kamat et al. (2017) assesses body postures in repetitive lifting, recommending ergonomic workspace improvements to prevent strain. This study discovered that frequent bending, twisting, and lifting from awkward positions contributes to significant levels of strain among workers in heavy lifting professions. The study found that modifying workspace arrangements, such as adjusting shelf heights and storage configurations, led to a significant improvement in ergonomic conditions. Reduced reach and more accessible positioning of heavier items resulted in fewer cases of musculoskeletal strain, demonstrating the advantages of environmental changes.

3. Use of Assistive Lifting Equipment

Assistive equipment can reduce the frequency of manual lifts for substantial objects, lowering bodily strain and preventing repetitive lifting accidents. The article "Assistive devices for manual materials handling in warehouses: a systematic literature review" by C.H. Glock et al. (2021) investigates the usefulness of assistive devices like dollies and lifts in minimizing ergonomic strain. This study revealed that assistance technologies, including as lifts and dollies, are extremely successful at minimizing ergonomic strain in warehouse settings. The study

discovered that using these devices reduced physical stress on workers by eliminating the need for manual lifting. Assistive gadgets were also associated to fewer occupational injuries, as well as enhanced efficiency and production. The review called for incorporating assistive technologies into workplaces with heavy lifting tasks to reduce ergonomic risks.

4. Regular Physical Conditioning and Exercise Programs

Implement optional or voluntary physical conditioning programs centered on core strengthening and flexibility exercises for personnel in lifting-intensive roles. The study "Effects of stretching exercise training and ergonomic modifications on musculoskeletal discomforts" by A. Shariat et al. (2018) investigates the effects of exercise routines in reducing ergonomic-related discomfort. In a randomized experiment, this study found that combining stretching exercises with ergonomic changes resulted in a significant reduction in musculoskeletal discomfort among workers. The operation relieved back and joint pain, which is commonly caused by repetitive or inappropriate lifting. The results imply that physical fitness, together with ergonomic improvements, effectively reduces musculoskeletal risks.

5. Rotational Shift to Minimize Fatigue

Schedule heavy lifting tasks such that they are rotated among employees rather than allocated frequently to the same people. Regular breaks and work rotation might also assist to relieve weariness. "Productivity and ergonomic risk in human-based production systems: A job-rotation scheduling model" by G. Mossa et al. (2016) explores work rotation as a strategy for balancing productivity with reduced

ergonomic risk. Workers reported lower levels of weariness after switching duties, which was directly associated to reduced ergonomic risk and increased workplace productivity. This paradigm promotes the use of scheduled rotations to reduce repetitive strain and improve overall worker well-being.

6. Periodic Ergonomic Assessments and Feedback Loops

Establish a regular plan for ergonomic examinations and invite employees to submit feedback on any difficulties they encounter while lifting. A.D. Banks and F. Aghazadeh's (2009) article "Progressive Fatigue Effects on Manual Lifting Factors" investigates the impact of fatigue in lifting tasks, recommending a supportive culture to recognize fatigue and emphasize safety. This study investigated the link between work duration and fatigue, discovering that extended lifting without breaks dramatically increases fatigue and the risk of injury. The study recommends creating a safety-first culture in which employees are encouraged to prioritize safety by taking breaks and reporting discomfort. Encouraging a culture that prioritizes safety above speed can result in long-term reductions in ergonomic risks and injuries in the workplace.

DEFINITION OF TERMS

1. Substantia gelatinosa - a tiny jelly-like control center nestled within the spinal cord and marked by its translucent appearance, plays a crucial role in how we experience pain.
2. Dorsal horn - a central hub for processing sensory information, especially pain that is nestled within the spinal cord.
3. Pain signals - It is an electrical message from injured tissue that travels through nerve pathways to the brain and it influences pain intensity and perception, it is crucial for understanding and managing pain.
4. Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort - it categorizes workplace-related musculoskeletal discomfort that identifies risk factors for specific tasks and environments and also helps prevent and manage work-related pains.
5. Ergonomic Training - Education and instruction provided to workers on safe lifting techniques, proper posture, and other ergonomic principles.

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APPENDIX A-1

INFORMED CONSENT

Name of Lead Researcher: Kelly M. Aglipa

Name of Organization: Cebu Technological University – Moalboal Campus

Name of Proposal: Assessing Ergonomic Practices for Enhanced Worker Safety in Hardware Store

This Informed Consent Form has two parts:

- Information Sheet (to share information about the research with you)
- Certificate of Consent (for signatures if you agree to take part)

You will be given a copy of the full Informed Consent Form

PART I: Information Sheet

Introduction

We are the students of the Cebu Technological University – Moalboal Campus taking up a Bachelor of Science in Industrial Engineering. We are currently conducting a study entitled: “Assessing Ergonomic Practices for Enhanced Worker Safety in Hardware Store”.

In line with this, we are inviting you to be one of our respondents to this investigation and request you to spare a few minutes of your time to answer this questionnaire honestly. However, you do not have to decide today whether or not you will participate in the research. Before you decide, you can talk to anyone you feel comfortable with about the research. If there are contents in the questionnaire that you do not understand and find ambiguous then feel free to contact the researcher. Rest assured that all the answers will be treated with utmost confidentiality.

Purpose of the research

In this research study it aims to investigate hardware store workers' experiences of pain or discomfort when lifting heavy objects or loads, and make recommendations to improve worker safety against musculoskeletal disorders in hardware stores.

Type of Research Intervention

This study will involve survey questionnaires and conduct direct observation based on the researcher – made tool.

Participant selection

We are inviting the porters in hardware store that involved in lifting heavy objects or loads, and who are currently employed in that industry.

Voluntary Participation

Your participation in this research is entirely voluntary. It is your choice whether to participate or not. Whether you choose to participate or not, it does not affect your identity as a worker. You may change your mind later and stop participating even if you agreed earlier and this will not be taken against you later on.

Procedures and Protocol

In this investigation, you will be asked to answer a questionnaire that will be distributed during your free time. It will be collected after you completely answer the questionnaire. The questionnaire can be read aloud and you can give the answer on those items that you intend to answer. The information recorded is confidential and no one else except the research adviser who will have the access to her/his questionnaire. The questionnaires will be destroyed after 6 months.

To ensure that you will be able to have full grasp on the purpose of the study, the proponent will first explain the objectives of the study and the intended benefits of the participants itself.

Duration

The research takes place within 6 months. Your engagement as a respondent will only take once.

Benefits

This study is beneficial not only to the porters of the hardware store but also to the manager and owner of the business. Through this study, together, they will determine the status of the porters regarding how the experience and deal in terms of musculoskeletal disorder and proper lifting.

Reimbursements

You will not be provided with any payment for taking part in the research.

Confidentiality

We, the researchers of this study, will not be sharing information about you. The information that we collect from this research will be kept confidential. Information about you and your perception that will be collected from this research will be put away and no one but the researcher will be able to see it. It will not be shared with or given to anyone except to the research adviser.

Sharing the Results

At the end of the study, we, the researchers of this study will be sharing what we have learned with the respondents. Nothing that you answered in the questionnaire will be shared with anybody outside the research. A written report will also be given to the participants whom they can share with their families. We will also publish the results in order for those interested people to learn from this research.

Right to Refuse or Withdraw

You may choose not to participate in this study and do not have to take part in this research if you do not wish to do so. Choosing to participate or not will not affect you as a resident in the community. You will still benefit from the possible action plan that we will propose based on the result of this study.

Who to Contact

If you have any questions, you can ask them now or later, even if the study has started. If you wish to ask questions later, you may contact any of the following:

Name of the Researcher	Phone Number
Principal Investigator: Kelly M. Aglipa	09608650434
Member: Caple Jey Yosores	09658960721

PART II: Certificate of Consent

I have read and understood the provided information and have had the opportunity to ask questions. I know that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving a reason and without cost. I voluntarily agree to take part in this study.

Respondent's Signature:

Date:

If illiterate

A literate witness must sign (if possible, this person should be selected by the participant and have no connection to the research team). Illiterate participants should include their thumbprints as well.

I have witnessed the accurate reading of the consent form to the potential participant, and the individual has had to ask questions. I confirm that the individual has given consent freely.

Name of witness:
Signature of witness:
Date:

Thumbprint of participant:

I confirm that the participant was allowed to ask questions about the study, and all the questions asked by the participant have been answered correctly to the best of my ability. I confirm that the individual has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent has been given freely and voluntarily.

Print name of researcher/person taking the consent:
Signature of researcher/person taking the consent:

RAPID ENTIRE BODY ASSESSMENT (REBA)

REBA Employee Assessment Worksheet

Task Name:

Date:

A. Neck, Trunk and Leg Analysis

Step 1: Locate Neck Position

Step 1a: Adjust...
If neck is twisted: +1
If neck is side bending: +1

Neck Score

Step 2: Locate Trunk Position

Step 2a: Adjust...
If trunk is twisted: +1
If trunk is side bending: +1

Trunk Score

Step 3: Legs

Leg Score

Step 4: Look-up Posture Score in Table A

Using values from steps 1-3 above, locate score in Table A

Posture Score A

Step 5: Add Force/Load Score

If load < 11 lbs.: +0
If load 11 to 22 lbs.: +1
If load > 22 lbs.: +2
Adjust: If shock or rapid build up of force: add +1

Force / Load Score

Step 6: Score A, Find Row in Table C

Add values from steps 4 & 5 to obtain Score A. Find Row in Table C.

Score A

Scoring

- 1 = Negligible Risk
- 2-3 = Low Risk. Change may be needed.
- 4-7 = Medium Risk. Further Investigate. Change Soon.
- 8-10 = High Risk. Investigate and Implement Change
- 11+ = Very High Risk. Implement Change

Scores

Table A		Neck											
		1				2				3			
Legs		1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
Trunk Posture Score	1	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	3	3	5	6
	2	2	3	4	5	3	4	5	6	4	5	6	7
	3	2	4	5	6	4	5	6	7	5	6	7	8
	4	3	5	6	7	5	6	7	8	6	7	8	9
Score		5	4	6	7	8	6	7	8	9	7	8	9

Table B		Lower Arm					
		1			2		
Wrist		1	2	3	1	2	3
Upper Arm Score	1	1	2	2	1	2	3
	2	2	1	2	3	2	3
	3	3	3	4	5	4	5
	4	4	4	5	5	6	7
	5	6	7	8	7	8	8
	6	7	8	8	8	9	9

Table C		Score B											
Score A	Score B												
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
1	1	1	1	2	3	3	4	5	6	7	7	7	
2	1	2	2	3	4	4	5	6	6	7	7	8	
3	2	3	3	3	4	5	6	7	7	8	8	8	
4	3	4	4	4	5	6	7	8	8	9	9	9	
5	4	4	4	5	6	7	8	8	9	9	9	9	
6	6	6	6	7	8	8	9	9	10	10	10	10	
7	7	7	7	8	9	9	9	10	10	10	11	11	
8	8	8	8	9	10	10	10	10	10	10	11	11	
9	9	9	9	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	11	11	
10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	11	11	
11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	12	12	
12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	

Table C Score + Activity Score = REBA Score

B. Arm and Wrist Analysis

Step 7: Locate Upper Arm Position:

Step 7a: Adjust...
If shoulder is raised: +1
If upper arm is abducted: +1
If arm is supported or person is leaning: -1

Upper Arm Score

Step 8: Locate Lower Arm Position:

Lower Arm Score

Step 9: Locate Wrist Position:

Wrist Score

Step 9a: Adjust...
If wrist is bent from midline or twisted: Add +1

Step 10: Look-up Posture Score in Table B

Using values from steps 7-9 above, locate score in Table B

Posture Score B

Step 11: Add Coupling Score

Well fitting Handle and mid rang power grip, **good: +0**
Acceptable but not ideal hand hold or coupling acceptable with another body part, **fair: +1**
Hand hold not acceptable but possible, **poor: +2**
No handles, awkward, unsafe with any body part, **Unacceptable: +3**

Coupling Score

Step 12: Score B, Find Column in Table C

Add values from steps 10 & 11 to obtain Score B. Find column in Table C and match with Score A in row from step 6 to obtain Table C Score.

Score B

Step 13: Activity Score

+1 1 or more body parts are held for longer than 1 minute (static)
+1 Repeated small range actions (more than 4x per minute)
+1 Action causes rapid large range changes in postures or unstable base

NIOSH LIFTING EQUATION

NIOSH Lifting Equation Manual Scoring Sheet

Date: _____	Task: _____
Company: _____	Supervisor: _____
Dept: _____	Evaluator: _____

ACTUAL MEASUREMENTS	Origin	Destination
Load Weight (L) (pounds)		
Load Constant (pounds)	51	51
Horizontal Location (H) (inches)		
Vertical Location (V) (inches)		
Vertical Travel Distance (Vo - Vd)		
Asymmetry Angle (A) (degrees)		
Lifting Duration (hours)		
Lifting Frequency (F) (lifts/minute)		
Coupling (C)		

RESULTS

	Origin	Destination
Recommended Weight Limit (RWL)		
Lifting Index (LI)		

$LI \leq 1$: This lift may be acceptable.

$1 < LI \leq 3$: This lift may increase the risk of low back or lifting injury. Controls should be considered.

$LI > 3$: This lift may exceed the capabilities of safely performing the lift for nearly all workers. Redesign of the lifting task is recommended.

Double circle worst case multiplier; single circle second worst case multiplier

H V D A F C

APPENDIX A-3

PROFILE OF THE WORKERS

Study Title: **Assessing Ergonomic Practices for Enhanced Worker Safety in Hardware Store**

Principal Investigator/Lead Researcher:

KELLY M. AGLIPA
Cebu Technological University
Moalboal Campus
09927855231/09608650434

In regards to the informed consent, we hereby pledge the security of your information.

Confidentiality: The data collected from you will be kept confidential and only used for research purposes. Your identity will not be revealed in any publications or reports resulting from this study. All data will be stored securely, and only authorized personnel will have access to it.

Here are the information we'd like to gather concerning the requirements needed for research purposes:

NAME:	
AGE:	
WORK EXPERIENCE:	

BMI: _____	WHO Adult BMI Categories	
	BMI	Category
Height: _____	< 16.0	Severely Underweight
	16.0 - 18.4	Underweight
Weight: _____	18.5 - 24.9	Normal
	25.0 - 29.9	Overweight
	30.0 - 34.9	Moderately Obese
	35.0 - 39.9	Severely Obese
	≥ 40.0	Morbidly Obese

Consent:

By signing this form, you agree to participate in this study and acknowledge that you have read and understood the information provided above.

Participant's Name (Printed): _____

Participant's Signature: _____

Date: _____

Investigator's Signature: _____

Date: _____

CURRICULUM VITAE

KELLY M. AGLIPA

Home Address: Poblacion Uno, Malabuyoc, Cebu

Email Address: kellyaglipa01@gmail.com

Contact Number: 09608650434

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Date of Birth: August 01, 2002
 Age: 22
 Civil Status: Single
 Citizenship: Filipino
 Religion: Roman Catholic

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Tertiary Engineering	Bachelor of Science in Industrial
Campus	Cebu Technological University - Moalboal
	Poblacion West, Moalboal, Cebu
Secondary	Perpetual Succour Academy, Inc.
	Poblacion Dos, Malabuyoc, Cebu
	S.Y. 2019 – 2020
Primary	Malabuyoc Central Elementary School
	Poblacion Dos, Malabuyoc, Cebu
	S.Y. 2013 – 2014

CURRICULUM VITAE

QUEENLY GRACE S. CABALLERO

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PERSONAL INFORMATION

Date of Birth: August 03, 2003
Age: 21
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Citizenship: Filipino
Religion: Roman Catholic

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Tertiary Engineering	Bachelor of Science in Industrial
Campus	Cebu Technological University - Moalboal
	Poblacion West, Moalboal, Cebu
Secondary	Tubod National High School
	Tubod, Badian, Cebu
	S.Y. 2020 – 2021
Primary	Tubod Elementary School
	Tubod, Badian, Cebu
	S.Y. 2014 – 2015

CURRICULUM VITAE

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PERSONAL INFORMATION

Date of Birth: May 09, 2003
 Age: 21
 Civil Status: Single
 Citizenship: Filipino
 Religion: Roman Catholic

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Tertiary Engineering	Bachelor of Science in Industrial
Campus	Cebu Technological University - Moalboal
	Poblacion West, Moalboal, Cebu
Secondary	Bitoon National Vocational High School
	Bitoon, Dumajug, Cebu
	S.Y. 2020 – 2021
Primary	Alcantara Central Elementary School
	Poblacion, Alcantara, Cebu
	S.Y. 2014 – 2015

CURRICULUM VITAE

LEEDY MAE Y. OMPOC

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PERSONAL INFORMATION

Date of Birth: November 29, 2002
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 Civil Status: Single
 Citizenship: Filipino
 Religion: Roman Catholic

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Tertiary Engineering	Bachelor of Science in Industrial
Campus	Cebu Technological University - Moalboal
	Poblacion West, Moalboal, Cebu
Secondary	Moalboal National High School
	Poblacion, Moalboal, Cebu
	S.Y. 2020 – 2021
Primary	Saavedra Elementary School
	Saavedra, Moalboal, Cebu
	S.Y. 2014 – 2015

CURRICULUM VITAE

LYNDE MAE J. SUERTE

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PERSONAL INFORMATION

Date of Birth: May 08, 2003
Age: 21
Civil Status: Single
Citizenship: Filipino
Religion: Roman Catholic

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Tertiary Engineering	Bachelor of Science in Industrial
Campus	Cebu Technological University - Moalboal
	Poblacion West, Moalboal, Cebu
Secondary	Badian National High School
	Poblacion, Badian, Cebu
	S.Y. 2020 – 2021
Primary	Basak Elementary School
	Basak, Badian, Cebu
	S.Y. 2014 – 2015